

Steric and Resonance Effects on the Kinetics of Oxidation of Organic Sulfides by Quinolinium Fluorochromate

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Kinetics of oxidation of dialkyl, alkyl phenyl and benzal methyl phenyl sulfides to their sulfoxides by quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) have been followed in aqueous acetic acid. The order of the reaction is found to be one each with respect to QFC, H₃O⁺ and the sulfide. Increase in the dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate, while variation in ionic strength has no perceptible change in the rate. The steric effect plays a dominant role to decide the rate of the reaction rather than the inductive effect. In the case of benzal methylphenyl sulfide, the larger rate is due to the resonance effect. Attack of protonated QFC on the organic sulfide in a slow step, is rate-determining one.

Benzal methylphenyl sulfide has two reactive sites susceptible for oxidation, viz. the double bond and the sulfide sulfur. In order to ascertain the preferential site of attack in the oxidation, kinetics of oxidation of benzal methylphenyl sulfide by quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) have been studied and the results are compared with those of dialkyl and alkyl phenyl sulfides. The mechanisms of the oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides involving polar transition states have been studied extensively. Halogenating agents are known to convert sulfides primarily into halogenosulfonium salts¹, and the intermediates with a positive sulfonium center have also been proposed for reactions of sulfides with peroxydisulfate², peroxydiphosphate³, pyridinium chlorochromate⁴, idosylbenzene diacetate⁵, sodium periodate⁶ and pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide⁷. The use of various sources of Cr^{VI} species for the oxidation of organic sulfides are well documented in the literature⁸. The mechanism of these oxidations is largely dependent on the nature of the oxidants. In this list of oxidation of organic sulfides, the use of quinolinium fluorochromate is a new addition.

Results and Discussion

In each case, the oxidation followed a first order kinetics both with respect to substrate and oxidant. Plots of log [QFC] versus time are linear with correlation coefficient (*r*), at least 0.994. The pseudo-first order rate constant

(*k*₁) remains almost constant at different [QFC]₀. Plots of *k*₁ versus [sulfide]₀ are linear, passing through the origin (each with *r* = 0.998). The order in [H₃O⁺] is one in accordance with the expectation, based on the involvement of protonated QFC in the mechanism. Added sodium perchlorate has no promising effect on the oxidation (Table 1). Added acrylonitrile did not induce any polymerization in the reaction mixture.

Effect of solvent composition : The oxidations of ethyl methyl, methyl phenyl and benzal methyl phenyl sulfides were studied in the solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid and water (Table 2). Increase in rate constant with decrease in dielectric constant is possible if there is an ion-molecule involvement in the rate-determining step. The solvent effect was analyzed using Grunwald-Winstein equation⁹, log *k*₂ = log *k*₀ + *mY*. The linear plot of log *k*₂ versus *Y* (each with *r* = 0.999) gives *m* values -0.70, -0.75 and -0.46, and log *k*₀ values of 0.21, 0.17 and -0.75 respectively, for ethyl methyl, methyl phenyl and benzal methyl phenyl sulfides. It is to be noted that these values of *m* are in consonance with an S_N2 type transition state propounded during the oxidation of organic sulfides¹⁰.

Effect of substituents : The rates of oxidation of six dialkyl, five alkyl phenyl and benzal methyl phenyl sulfides were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated (Table 3). When comparing the reactivities of dialkyl sulfides containing different alkyl

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF ETHYL METHYL, METHYL PHENYL AND BENZAL METHYLPHENYL SULFIDES AT 35°

[Sulphide]	[QFC]	[HClO ₄]	[NaClO ₄]	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₁ (s ⁻¹)			<i>n</i>
				EtSMe ^a	PhSMe ^a	PhCH=CHSPH ^b	
10 ² M	10 ³ M	10 ² M	10 ² M				
0.5-1.5	0.5	20	-	7.2-21.7	-	-	5
1.0	0.5-1.5	20	-	14.4-12.6	-	-	5
1.0	1.0	10-50	-	7.4-35.9	-	-	5
1.0	1.0	20	0-4.0	14.2-14.3	-	-	5
0.5-1.5	0.5	50	-	-	6.1-18.3	-	5
1.0	0.5-1.5	50	-	-	12.3-10.7	-	5
1.0	1.0	40-80	-	-	8.8-17.5	-	5
1.0-4.0	1.0	0.5	-	-	-	10.8-41.2	7
1.0	0.5-2.0	0.5	-	-	-	10.8-10.6	4
1.0	1.0	0.5-1.5	-	-	-	10.8-33.1	5

^a60% (v/v) aqueous AcOH. ^b80% (v/v) aqueous AcOH. *n* = Number of data points.

groups, a decrease in the reaction rate was observed with increasing bulkiness of the alkyl substituent, in the order, $\text{Me}_2\text{S} > \text{EtSMe} > \text{Et}_2\text{S} > n\text{-Pr}_2\text{S} > n\text{-Bu}_2\text{S} > \text{iso-Pr}_2\text{S}$. The observed second order rate constants for the oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides, PhSR ($R = \text{Me, Et, n-Pr, iso-Pr, t-Bu}$) reveal that the rate decreases in the order, $\text{PhSMe} > \text{PhSEt} > \text{PhSn-Pr} > \text{PhSiso-Pr} > \text{PhSt-Bu}$. If the contribution of +I effect of alkyl group predominates over its steric effect, exerted by the increasing bulkiness of the alkyl group, the order would have shown a reverse trend. Furthermore, there is a good correlation between $\log(k_2/k_2(\text{Me}))$ values with Taft's steric substituent constants¹¹, E_s ($r = 0.996$).

TABLE 2 - EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION RATE AT 35°

AcOH % (v/v)	γ^*	$10^2 k^2 (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$		
		EtSMe	PhSMe	PhCH=CHSPH
40	2.31	3.6	2.7	-
50	1.96	7.2	5.3	-
60	1.52	14.2	11.0	-
70	0.99	31.0	25.6	-
75	0.77	-	-	6.1
80	0.50	72.6	63.3	7.8
85	0.19	-	-	14.2
90	-0.17	-	-	21.1

*Values from Ref. 9.

TABLE 3 - RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE OXIDATION OF SULFIDES BY QFC

Sulfide	$10^2 k_2 (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$					ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°		
RSR':							
MeSMe	14.0	18.1	22.9	27.7	32.1	31.5	157.4
EtSMe	10.0	14.2	18.4	22.8	26.5	36.9	141.9
EtSEt	9.8	13.7	17.8	20.9	24.7	34.4	150.3
n-PrSn-Pr	8.8	11.9	15.2	19.1	24.4	38.2	139.3
n-BuSn-Bu	6.9	9.9	13.2	16.1	21.3	42.1	128.2
iso-PrSiso-Pr	-	4.4	6.0	7.8	9.5	40.4	139.8
PhSR:							
PhSMe	7.7	11.0	14.2	18.4	23.6	42.2	127.0
PhSEt	5.9	7.9	11.9	14.9	20.1	47.2	112.6
PhSn-Pr	-	6.6	9.3	11.9	17.1	48.7	109.8
PhSiso-Pr	-	4.8	6.7	8.8	13.2	51.7	102.8
PhSt-Bu	-	2.9	4.0	6.0	8.4	57.4	88.6
PhCH=CHSPH	6.8	8.7	10.4	12.4	14.2	33.1	158.7

An analysis of the rates of oxidation of these alkyl phenyl sulfides was made using Pavelich-Taft DSP equation¹²,

$$\log k = \rho \cdot \sigma^* + \delta E_s + h$$

The small positive polar reaction constant at each temperature (Table 4) would mean that the electron-donating power of the alkyl group does not enhance the rate. Thus the steric factor seems to play a dominant role rather than +I effect of the alkyl group. From the observed rate constants of the oxidation of benzal methyl phenyl and methyl phenyl sulfides, it is seen that the rate of oxidation of benzal methylphenyl sulfide is very fast (16.4 times) than that of methyl phenyl sulfide.

TABLE 4 - CORRELATION DATA ON THE RATES OF OXIDATION OF ALKYL PHENYL SULFIDES USING PAVELICH-TAFT DSP EQUATION*

Temp. °C	ρ	δ	R	SD	n
35	0.06	1.66	0.995	0.016	5
40	0.12	1.27	0.980	0.031	5
45	0.05	1.42	0.974	0.030	5
50	0.11	0.98	0.988	0.019	5

* R = Coefficient of multiple correlation; SD = standard deviation; n = number of data points.

Brown and Okamoto¹³ developed σ_p^+ constants for substituents conjugated with the reaction centre, which could effectively delocalize a positive charge. The σ_p^+ constants can be used in the equation, $\sigma_p = \sigma_I + \sigma_R$, to define R^+ , regarded as resonance constant¹⁴. The R^+ values for methyl phenyl and benzal methyl phenyl sulfides are -0.32 and -1.10 respectively. It is evident hence that the large negative value of resonance constant, due to the large conjugation is responsible for the faster oxidation rate in benzal methyl phenyl sulfide¹⁵.

Mechanism: The nucleophilic attack of a sulfide sulfur on a QFC oxygen may be viewed as an S_N2 process. A low magnitude of polar reaction constant supports a transition state as depicted in 1, rather than a plausible sulphonium ion involvement as shown in 2 (Scheme 1). The solvent effect also supports an S_N2 like transition state. Such a mechanism involving the rate-determining electrophilic oxygen transfer from QFC to the sulfide [situation 1], seems to be similar to those suggested for the oxidation of sulfides and iodide ions by periodate ion^{6,16}, and for the oxidation of sulfides by hydrogen peroxide¹⁷.

Scheme 1

The oxidation of sulfides by QFC may involve a cyclic intermediate as has been suggested in many reactions involving Cr^{VI} ¹⁸. However, the cyclic intermediates may also exhibit a sulfurane structure (3). The cyclic intermediate would be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone-pair of electrons or an alkyl group. In that case, the steric requirements of the situation 3 would be larger than those of 1 and the observed higher values of steric reaction constants are inconsistent with the proposed cyclic sulfurane mechanism. The ΔS^\ddagger values (Table 3) are

in parallel with the corresponding values measured for typical reactions involving oxygen transfer, e.g. for the oxidation of iodide ions by periodate¹⁶ and that of sulfides by hydrogen peroxide¹⁷ and periodate⁶ ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -96, -115$ and $-113 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively).

The rate law for the suggested mechanism is

$$-d[\text{QFC}]/dt = K_1 k_2 [\text{Sulfide}][\text{QFC}][\text{H}^+]$$

and the pseudo-first order rate constant,

$$k_1 = K_1 k_2 [\text{Sulfide}][\text{H}^+].$$

Experimental

The sulfides were prepared using standard methods and distilled before use. QFC was prepared by known procedure¹⁹. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

The experiment was carried out by mixing the substrate and oxidant solutions under pseudo-first order condition in requisite quantity of aqueous acetic acid. For all the sulfides other than benzal methyl phenyl sulfide, the kinetics were followed spectrophotometrically at 360 nm. Since benzal methyl phenyl sulfide was coloured, its kinetics were followed by estimating the unreacted QFC iodometrically. The kinetic studies were followed nearly upto 85% reaction.

Stoichiometry of the reaction for all the sulfides was found to be 1 : 1. Product analysis under kinetic conditions gave only the sulfoxide in each case of study, which was confirmed by ir frequency ($\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ for EtSOMe, PhSOMe and PhSOCH=CHPh were 1051, 1055 and 1053 cm^{-1} respectively).

References

1. F. RUFF and A. KUCCSMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1975, 509; 1982, 1075.
2. C. SRINIVASAN, P. KUTHALINGAM, and N. ARUMUGAM, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 382.
3. C. SRINIVASAN, P. KUTHALINGAM, and N. ARUMUGAM, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1980, 170.
4. G. P. PANIGRAHI and D. D. MAHAPATRO, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1981, **13**, 85.
5. C. SRINIVASAN, A. CHELLAMANI, and P. KUTHALINGAM, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **47**, 428.
6. F. RUFF and A. KUCCSMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 683.
7. K. KARUNAKARAN and K. P. ELANGO, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **8**, 429.
8. C. SRINIVASAN, A. CHELLAMANI, and S. RAJAGOPAL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 1201; K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 2065; G. MANGALAM and SP. MEENKSHISUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 77; K. RAJASEKARAN, T. BASKARAN, and C. GNANASEKARAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1984, 1183.
9. A. H. FALNBERG and S. WINSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2770.
10. P. SYKES, "A Guidebook to Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Orient Longman, New Delhi, 1988, p. 391.
11. R. W. TAFT, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1956, Chap. 13.
12. W. A. PAVELICH and R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4935.
13. H. C. BROWN and Y. OKAMOTO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4980.
14. C. HANCH and A. LEO, "Substituents Constants for Correlation Analysis in Chemistry and Biology", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1979.
15. C. HANCH, A. LEO, and R. W. TAFT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 165.
16. A. INDELLI, F. FERRANTI, and F. SECCO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 631.
17. G. MODENA and L. MAIOLI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1957, **87**, 1306.
18. Y. W. CHANG and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1401; J. ROCEK and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 2241.
19. V. MURUGESAN and A. PANDURANGAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 377.